

ORGANIZING A SYSTEM OF SAFE WORK IN INDUSTRIAL ENTERPRISES, ORGANIZING A MANAGEMENT SYSTEM.

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Abstract. The issue of security management has a special place in the provision of security in the country, its situation plays an important role in the adoption of various socio-economic and political decisions, security management is of great importance for every country.

Keywords: Safety, protection, stability, risk, protection, injury, technical, organizational, noise, gases, accidents.

The urgency of ensuring security is accompanied by its national and regional security, issues of ensuring stability, the main threat in the modern conditions of the world community and any changes in the security system, the manifestation of various dangers and threats. Therefore, the issue of protection management and prevention of modern dangers and threats arises. It is at this stage that it is necessary to protect people from the negative effects of various harmful, dangerous factors during their activities. The problems of increasing work productivity and improving the quality of products remain one of the most important issues facing humanity. Relevance of the topic. In all enterprises and organizations, it is necessary to successfully solve the problems of creating comfortable and healthy working conditions for workers, preventing various risks, protecting them from various negative factors, and developing ways to reduce injuries. Objects of professional activity of labor protection: organization of safe and healthy working conditions in economic sectors, quick action of people in dangerous situations, emergency situations, means and technologies to avoid them during natural and man-made disasters, measures aimed at preventing their occurrence, emergency situations, etc. It consists in creating regulatory legal frameworks aimed at coordinating the measures to eliminate them and the issues of life safety [1].

Management of labor safety is carried out on the basis of the preparation and implementation of a system of a number of organizational, technical, sanitary-hygienic and economic measures. The main task of the labor safety service is to eliminate the causes of injuries and other misfortunes that occur in production, and to monitor the improvement of the working conditions of the organization's administration to the employees, and to implement labor safety and protective equipment based on the introduction of scientific and technical achievements. development and implementation of organizational, technical and sanitary measures aimed at improving work culture, preventing accidents [2].

Principles-it is an idea, a thought, general concepts and general rules. The way that comes from the general rules and leads to the goal is the way to achieve the goal. Safety principles. The principles that ensure safety are different and can be divided into such groups as orientational, technical, organizational, and management. Guiding principles include worker activity, humaneness of operations, operator rotation, classification, risk elimination,

systematization, risk reduction, etc. Principles of reporting. It is based on providing guidelines and instructions to the worker on ensuring safety during work. This includes course readings, walkthroughs, safety signs, warning signs, and more [2,3].

Methods of ensuring security. Before studying safety methods, let's talk about terms like working zone and danger zone. The place where the worker stands or moves during the labor process, the working zone is called the homosphere. It is called zonanoxosphere, where danger occurs constantly or periodically.

Methods of ensuring safety during the labor process can be divided into the following 3 types:

- To separate homosphere and noxosphere in space and (or) time based method. This is mainly done through remote control, automation, robotization and other organizational measures.

- The method of normalizing the noxosphere by eliminating the risk. To this includes a set of measures and team protective equipment aimed at protecting people from noise, gases, and dust.

- It is aimed at increasing the level of human protection in a certain environment a set of methods and tools. This method is implemented through training of workers on safety techniques, use of danger zone, psychological influence and other similar measures. Safety devices -It is the material embodiment of the constructive, organizational structure of the implementation of security principles and methods. Safety equipment is divided into collective protective equipment (PPE) and personal protective equipment (PPE). On the other hand, TPE and PPEIar are divided into several groups depending on the nature of the risk, the procedure of implementation, the field of use and similar indicators. Accounting for accidents caused by improperly organized management. The influence of unpleasant factors of the production environment or labor process is crucial in the origin of occupational diseases. The clinical appearance of most occupational diseases does not have specific symptoms, therefore, accurate information about the working conditions of the sick person helps to determine the etiological role of the occupational factor in the origin of the disease. Occupational diseases are the result of harmful factors of one or another occupational production on the human body (for example, silicon dioxide dust in silicosis, industrial toxic substances in poisoning, etc.). Occupational diseases are divided into 5 groups by etiology:

1. Diseases developed under the influence of chemical factors:sharp and chronic poisonings and complications, skin diseases (contact dermatitis, photodermatitis, toxic melanoderma, etc.)

2. Diseases developed due to the effect of industrial aerosols: pneumoconiosis, silicosis, siderosilicosis, anthracosilicosis, asbestosis, carboconiosis, dusty bronchitis, etc.

3. Diseases developed due to physical factors: vibration sickness, electroophthalmia. cataract, cochlear neuritis, light disease, etc.

4. Physical stress: related to the stress of organs and systems diseases:coordinator neuroses, peripheral nervous system diseases, neck and lumbar radiculopathy, shoulder epicondylitis, etc. Diseases (chronic laryngitis) caused by the downward movement of the uterus, varicose veins in the legs, straining of the vocal cords, etc.

5. Diseases developed under the influence of biological factors:infectious and parasitic diseases - tuberculosis, brucellosis, viral hepatitis, dysbacteriosis, skin candidomycosis, visceral candidomycosis, etc. In addition to these etiological groups,

occupational allergic (conjunctivitis, rhinopharyngitis, bronchial asthma, dermatitis, eczema, etc.) and oncological (skin, oral cavity, tumors of respiratory organs, leukemia, etc.) diseases there is.

Classification of occupational diseases can be as follows:

1. Communicable diseases: These types of diseases are only in physical cases can appear, limit physical activity, affect traffic. For example, osteochondrosis, arthritis, osteoporosis;

2. Occupational diseases: These types of diseases are related to people's work related to limiting their activities and affecting their coming to work. For example, such as back pain and hand cramps caused by long hours of work at the desk or computer;

3. Professional diseases: These types of diseases are specific are common diseases among people who are close. For example, finger crushing or flooding volume can occur in large flower and water sellers.

The reasons for the origin can be as follows:

1. Physical factors: Correct working position, restraint, transition, hands can be caused by physical causes such as

2. Psychological reasons: Job stress, job satisfaction, job dissatisfaction, can arise from reasons related to maneuver and psychological problems and educational manifestations;

3. Chemo-nuclear factors: Chemical wealth, with harmful chemical elements can open the way to diseases while working;

4. Biological and genetic causes: Some diseases are passed down in previous generations possible

5. Social factors: Bad working conditions, conflicts at work, may be due to reasons such as security issues. The labor safety management system is extensive can be studied as a complex, multi-factorial, multi-level phenomenon that takes place in space [4].

The author of the study process used the categorical-symbolic "black box" model, which is successfully used in scientific research in many fields, but is not yet fully used in research in the field of labor protection. This process was carried out through the development of the Labor Protection model that meets the requirements of the modern economy, reflects the essence of its reform process, and identifies the main factors affecting the change of the labor protection system in the country, region or enterprise. It is necessary to consider the study of the labor safety management system within the framework of the methodology of systematic analysis, to give a more precise definition of the concept of "systematicity", to clarify its three aspects: system theory, systematic approach and system concepts. System-it is a set of interconnected and interacting elements, in which the power of internal relations between them is greater than the power of external relations and has a new embodied character, different from the nature, for a certain purpose or is a directed complex. Its elements: an integral part of the system, which is understood as an independent object that cannot be separated from the point of view of its external characteristics [5].

These include: - real objects (enterprise, energy, product, etc.) - information on information system elements and system status; - conscious objects - a state of things that is consciously described. Researchers describe the current labor protection system as consisting of three functional directions: supply, management and a set of blocks of elements that reflect

the features of economic provision and management. represents the necessary resources for protection and includes the following types:

- Legal;
- Economic;
- Social;
- Information.

The control block represents the relevant processes and links: - Management of labor safety (to create management systems the fundamental process in organizing based labor protection); - management of professional risks (the level of professional risks of employees a set of interrelated activities aimed at detection, assessment and reduction). The block of elements of the labor safety management system, these are: - industrial sanitation and safety; - technical aesthetics; - ergonomics and others. The external environment of the labor safety management system can include the conditions of the modern economy determined by external economic, social, political, scientific and technical, legal, man-made, natural, ecological, investment, innovative, information and market factors. The concept of labor safety management is a continuous process of complex changes in the elements of the labor protection system, with the content, time, resources, positive results and maximum efficiency indicators, with the prospects of achieving short-term and long-term goals in labor protection at the micro and macroeconomic levels in the development of organizational-production-technical technological, economic-social and management structures are interrelated to the changing processes in the external and internal environments [6].

Summary one of the main conditions for the existence, survival and development of human society is the carrying out of various forms of activity in it. The subject conducting the activity is only a person with consciousness and thinking. There is a form of activity that is of the greatest importance for society. This is considered the highest form of activity - labor. Because all the material, spiritual and other wealth of humanity is created only due to work. They include practical, intellectual and spiritual processes that take place in life, social life, culture, production, science and other spheres of life. In order to improve the quality and productivity of his work, man constantly changes and perfects his tools and means of production. As a result, he is under the influence of various harmful and dangerous factors that constantly arise in the work process, protection of the life, health and work ability of workers in production, prevention of various accidents, injuries and occupational diseases, comfortable and safe serves to create working conditions, design, develop and implement safe machines and mechanisms, devices, equipment.

With the above considerations in mind, I suggest: modern digital. for the operation and development of the labor safety management system in the economic environment, socio-economic, innovation, investment attraction, control of information flow, automation of labor protection processes and identification of robotization of the most dangerous workplaces. Occupational safety management mechanisms can be used both for a deeper study of the change and for further modeling of different scenarios in the change. Organization of safe and healthy working conditions in industrial enterprises, economic sectors, quick action of people in dangerous situations, emergency situations, means and technologies for prevention during natural and man-made disasters, development of measures aimed at their prevention, comfortable work for employees it is necessary to create conditions, organize management of labor protection.

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